

British Academy

Data management plan required?	Yes. (Although not required if no electronic data is to be produced). Data should be made freely available during and beyond the lifetime of the project.
RDM policy Link	No
Definition of data	Electronic or digital data (including datasets)
Length of data management plan	500 words
DMP template/ requirements	Details of how data will be stored and accessed.
Required data repository	Not specified
Time for data release	Not specified
Time for long-term storage of data	Not specified
Costings	Not specified
Last updated	Not known
Contact Details	grants@britac.ac.uk
Comments	N/A

Documents used: Notes for applicants (For Leverhulme trust but is applicable to a number of other grant schemes)

<https://www.thebritishacademy.ac.uk/sites/default/files/SRF%20Notes%20for%20Applicants%202018-19.pdf>

Accessed: May 2018